

PSYCHOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF DECREASING STUDY MOTIVATION IN STUDENTS

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Abstract: This article describes the psychological characteristics of the decrease in academic motivation among students

Key words: Motivation, education, pedagogue, psychology, character, temperament.

Introduction.

In the era of globalization, educating the young generation in the spirit of national pride and patriotism, taking a serious approach to their education is the need of the hour. It is necessary to increase the psychological approach and motivation of the future youth, especially students, to become qualified staff. In the age of advanced technology, it is very common to see cases of students getting bored during the learning process and learning motivation decreasing. For this reason, it is important to study the psychological characteristics of the decrease in academic motivation among students

While studying at the university, the student, first of all, faces a number of problems related to adaptation to the new didactic situation, the forms and methods of organizing the educational process, which are fundamentally different from school education. This approach and the difficulties associated with it create a unique didactic obstacle that must be overcome. It follows that the formation of positive motives and reasonable goals is important in the development of the personality of a future specialist, because motives and goals are important determinants of activity. The structure of the student's motivations formed during the teaching process becomes the basis of the personality of the future specialist. Therefore, the development of positive educational motives is an integral part of the education of the student's personality.

In the modern education process, in the first place, it is necessary not only to teach the student certain skills, knowledge and skills, but also to form the character and individuality of the person, which reflects the result of the educational process, and to develop the system of the needs and motives of the person. This, in turn, is an indicator of the quality of education. Educational motivation is of great importance in the development of students. The main role in its development is played by the professor-teacher. The most important condition for the formation of the student's educational motivation is his understanding of the meaning of his educational activity, his importance for him personally. Interest in the content of the educational material and the educational activity itself can be formed only if the student has the opportunity to show intellectual independence and initiative in the student community, which is very important. The more active the student's creative teaching methods and understanding of the subject being studied, the easier it is to interest the student, while the unquestionable presentation of ready-made material does not arouse their interest, although it does not interfere with the topic. It follows that the main means of forming a stable interest in learning is the teacher's use of questions and assignments that require

students to actively search, or in other words, to be independent. A positive correlation between motivational orientations and learning success has been identified in studies conducted by psychologists of school-aged students. The greatest success in education is ensured by being process-oriented and result-oriented. As a student, psychologist N.S. According to Leites, activity in general is mainly selective and is inextricably linked with the development of abilities.

M. V. Matyukhina distinguishes two types of motives depending on the sources of educational motivation: 1. internal - cognitive and social needs (desire for socially approved actions and achievements); 2. external - determined by the life conditions of the student, which include requirements, expectations and opportunities (requirements are related to the need to comply with social behavior, communication and activity norms); internal, external and personal educational motivation the interaction of resources affects the nature of educational activity and its results. The absence of one of the sources leads to a change in the system of educational motives or their deformation. The process of motivation consists of the following mental processes: perception of the content of the motive, emotional evaluation of its personal content, understanding and evaluation of the content of the motive, conviction of the motive. The content of the motive depends on the type of motive. The content of internal motives is the student's knowledge of the importance of the studied material in his worldview, in his knowledge of this object, in his practical activities. The perception of this knowledge creates the corresponding ideas in the mind of the student. So, the content of the motive is its objective basis. The subjective basis of the motive is the value of the educational material for a person with individual characteristics. Subjective meaning is formed on the basis of comparison of the objective meaning with the subjective value system and emotional experience of the real, human, personal meaning of the subject. The latter should be illustrated with concrete examples at the level of art, which arouse empathy, present serious but solvable problems, challenge the system of knowledge and lead to a general understanding or further knowledge of the object and the use of knowledge about it. affects the prospects. . Historical data, cases from practice, the fate of literary heroes, etc. are examples of this. The interaction of internal, external and personal sources of educational motivation affects the nature of educational activity and its results. . The absence of one of the sources leads to a change in the system of educational motives or their deformation. The process of motivation consists of the following mental processes: perception of the content of the motive, emotional evaluation of its personal content, understanding and evaluation of the content of the motive, confidence in the motive is important.

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